

IDEAS OF TEACHING LANGUAGES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION (METHODOLOGY, TEACHING METHODS)

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Abstract. The article presents the methodology of mastering the English language by preschool children English insight for kids (intuitive English for children) through play activities, where the author defined the goals and objectives of preschool education in teaching English, as well as the classification of foreign games (J. Piaget, etc.) and domestic scientists (L.S.Vygotsky, S.L. Rubinstein, D.B. Elkonin), where the advantages of playing techniques in the process of acquiring certain skills in English are emphasized. Within the framework of the English insight for kids methodology, games were classified into blocks, taking into account the psychological characteristics of preschool children. The following game blocks were identified: learning by seeing, learning by moving, learning by listening.

Keywords: learning by moving, listening, mastering, consolidation and activation of the English vocabulary, mastering a certain number of simple grammatical structures, building a coherent statement.

ИДЕИ ОБ ОБУЧЕНИИ ЯЗЫКАМ В ДОШКОЛЬНОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ (МЕТОДОЛОГИЯ, МЕТОДИКА ОБУЧЕНИЯ)

Аннотация. В статье представлена методика овладения английским языком дошкольниками English Insight for kids (интуитивный английский для детей) через игровую деятельность, где автором определены цели и задачи дошкольного образования в обучении английскому языку, а также классификация иноязычных игр. (Ж. Пиаже и др.) и отечественных ученых (Л. С. Выготский, С. Л. Рубинштейн, Д. Б. Эльконин), где подчеркиваются преимущества игровых приемов в процессе приобретения определенных навыков владения английским языком. В рамках методики English Insight for kids игры были разбиты на блоки с учетом психологических особенностей детей дошкольного возраста. Были выделены следующие игровые блоки: обучение, видя, обучение, двигаясь, обучение, слушая.

Ключевые слова: обучение в движении, аудирование, усвоение, закрепление и активизация английской лексики, усвоение определенного количества простых грамматических конструкций, построение связного высказывания.

INTRODUCTION

At present, mastering the English language is one of the important and promising tasks of modern pedagogy, and with all the variety of teaching aids, methodological developments for mastering a foreign language by children of preschool age, the question of choosing a methodology, setting goals and objectives of preschool education remains unresolved. Over the past few years, learning a foreign language has become not so much a way of self-development as a necessity. A foreign language has become a compulsory component of education not only in schools and universities, but also in many additional preschool institutions. The demand for a foreign language in society, on the one hand, as well as the understanding by parents that language is not only a factor in the education of a modern person, but also the basis of his social and material well-being in society - on the other hand, at the moment make early learning a

foreign language especially popular and relevant. If 20 years ago, knowledge of the language was required only in the work of some areas, now, possession of at least one foreign language is mandatory.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The main problem of teaching a foreign language is the age of the learner. It is known for certain that children are more amenable to learning. Until recently, the teaching methodology was aimed at school-age children, but now parents strive to start learning a foreign language as early as possible.

The main goals in teaching preschoolers a foreign language are:

- Formation of primary communication skills in a foreign language in children;
- the ability to use a foreign language to achieve their goals, to express thoughts and feelings in real communication situations;
- creation of a positive attitude towards the further study of foreign languages;
- awakening interest in the life and culture of other countries.

RESULTS

Preschool age is especially favorable for starting the study of a foreign language: children of this age are distinguished by a special sensitivity to linguistic phenomena, they have an interest in understanding their speech experience, the "secrets" of the language. They easily and firmly memorize a small amount of linguistic material and reproduce it well. With age, these favorable factors lose their strength. There is another reason why an early age is preferable for studying a foreign language. The younger the child, the less his vocabulary in his native language, but at the same time his speech needs are less: the spheres of communication in a small child are less than in an older child, he still does not have to solve complex communication problems. This means that, while mastering a foreign language, he does not feel such a huge gap between the possibilities in his native and foreign languages, and his feeling of success will be brighter than that of older children. Teaching kids is a very difficult matter that requires a completely different methodological approach than teaching schoolchildren and adults. If an adult speaks a foreign language, this does not mean at all that he can teach others. Faced with methodically helpless lessons, children can acquire an aversion to a foreign language for a long time and lose faith in their abilities. Only experienced professionals should work with preschoolers.

At preschool age, when teaching English in children, there is a gradual development of the foundations of communicative competence, which at an early stage of learning English includes the following aspects:

- the ability to correctly repeat English words from a phonetic point of view after a teacher, native speaker or speaker, that is, the gradual formation of auditory attention, phonetic hearing and correct pronunciation;
- mastering, consolidation and activation of the English vocabulary;
- mastering a certain number of simple grammatical structures, building a coherent statement.

DISCUSSION

The methodology for conducting direct educational activities should be built taking into account the age and individual characteristics of the structure of the linguistic abilities of children and should be aimed at their development. Communication in a foreign language should be motivated and focused. It is necessary to create in the child a positive psychological attitude

towards foreign language, and the way to create such a positive motivation is to play. Play is both a form of organization and a method of conducting classes in which children accumulate a certain stock of English vocabulary, memorize many poems, songs, counting rhymes, etc.

Cartoons in English are one of the best helpers in teaching English. Children love cartoons and enjoy watching them many times in a row. Therefore, cartoons in English help to solve many problems of teaching a foreign language to kids at once:

- the child does not have a question “why learn these words”;
- he is interested in watching a cartoon and he is happy to repeat the phrases of the characters;
- cartoons help the child not only learn and learn new words, but also master the sounds of English speech;
- repetition - if the child liked the cartoon, he is ready to watch the same cartoon over and over again until he learns it by heart.

This form of conducting classes creates favorable conditions for mastering language skills and speech skills. The ability to rely on play activity allows you to provide natural motivation for speech in a foreign language, to make even the most elementary statements interesting and meaningful. Playing in teaching a foreign language does not oppose educational activity, but is organically linked to it. Games in direct educational activities should not be episodic and isolated. An end-to-end play technique is needed that combines and integrates other activities in the process of language learning. The game methodology is based on the creation of an imaginary situation and the adoption by a child or teacher of a particular role. Educational games are divided into situational, competitive, rhythmic-musical and artistic.

- Situational are role-playing games that simulate communication situations on a particular occasion. Role-playing is a play activity during which children play certain roles, various life situations are played out, for example: a seller-buyer, a doctor-patient, an actor and his admirer, etc. They, in turn, are divided into games of a reproductive nature, when children reproduce a typical, standard dialogue, applying it to a particular situation, and improvisational games that require the application and modification of various models.

Standard dialogs for example:

- Show me (show me) - when the teacher names the subject, and the child must go to the card with the image of the desired word and point to it.
 - What’s this? The teacher shows words, children name words.
 - What’s missing? (what's missing)
 - What’s doesn’t belong? (which is superfluous)
- "Magic Mirror" - goal: development of attention. Children in animal masks approach the mirror. Several animals are reflected in the magic mirror. Children need to be told who they see and how much. For example: I see a dog. I see five dogs.

CONSLUSIONS

Most games that promote vocabulary and literacy are competitive. The winner in them is the one who has the best command of the language material. These are all kinds of crosswords, "auctions", board-printed games with linguistic tasks, command execution. Crosswords can be on any topic: animals, fruits, vegetables, furniture, toys, etc. There are different teams. In the classroom, children can play the game: “Simon says” - the purpose of this game is to develop cognitive interests. Children stand next to the teacher. The task of the children is to follow the

commands of the teacher. For example: Hands up! Sit down! Jump! Run! Etc. In the course of this game, lexical material of various topics is used.

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